

Self myofascial release (SMR) at volleyball players

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Abstract

The article presents the method of self-therapy of volleyball players which helps to improve the disposition on the court. There were indicated the benefits of self myofascial release. The basic issues of human physiology and the application of the knowledge in practice have been explained. There were described briefly a mechanism of pain reduction and normalization of muscle tension. Furthermore the importance of rolling for the prophylaxis of motion organ was described as well. There was mentioned the problem of muscle fatigue which concerns professional volleyball players and the alternative method of body regeneration. It was also discussed the point of choosing the equipment and the use of selected accessories in practice. The essay also shows the methodology of performing massage and selected most frequent areas requiring therapy.

Keywords: Self myofascial release (SMR), volleyball players

1. Background

Muscle pains of varying intensity can occur at any time, regardless of the intensity of physical activity. They makes it difficult to perform daily activities, significantly reducing the quality of life, and if they concerns a professional athlete, the problem can make it difficult or even impossible to practicing his profession. It is obvious that a professional athlete who spends 15-25 hours per week in training is much more exposed to suffer from undesirable symptoms from the movement apparatus. Minor injuries, pain or ordinary tiredness are the consequences of the work done, practically felt every day, after every training unit. Kilometers that have been run, thousands of repetitive jumps and squats heavily expose the body of the athlete leaving a harvest on almost every structure. No one can disagree with the philosopher of ancient Greece, who used to says that "movement is life, life is motion," because it is a movement we need for healthy functioning like we need water or oxygen. However, controversial is a well-known modern statement, saying "sport is health". That's because when we talk about sports, we must also think about rivalry, fighting for the best results that are achieved through hard training, which as it was previously mentioned has a negative impact on the athlete's body [1].

Every volleyball player strives to be better and better every day. In order to achieve this, he must take care of his own health first. However, this aspect is strongly underestimated by people who have never had injuries that cause absenteeism for longer periods of time in training.

SMR is especially appreciated by athletes who have experienced injuries in the past or who are looking for additional ways to improve their skills and improve their athletic posture. Self Myofascial Release, can help to achieve better results on the court, and when is correctly made, it contribute to reduce pain, significantly accelerates regeneration and is a component of anti-traumatic prevention [2].

2. Treatment

As regards treatment, the reduction of pain and the elimination of the cause of its occurrence should be taken into account. To cope with the pain by ourselves, first of all we must learn about the pathomechanism of the formation of these ailments. Fascia is a structure, which is made up of connective tissue. This tissue surrounds muscles, bones, nerves and internal organs, like the perfectly fitted suit, which is also separating them from each other. By providing unity and cushioning while moving, it acts as a scaffolding and as a protection. When it is properly nourished and hydrated, it gives the opportunity to slip structures between each other, thus ensuring the correct range of motion in the joints and proper muscle work. Constant repetitive activities and high intensity exercise interfere with the correct mechanics of this slip and cause fascial stiffening. Self Myofascial Release stimulates Golgi tendon organs located in fascia and tendons. Compression causes loosening the structure and also influence correctly to the improvement of the sliding between them by hydration. Self Myofascial Release, which is carried out with the use of

instruments for massage, carries many benefits associated with the influence of sports and classic massage, among others:

- It stimulates the blood circulation
- It accelerates tissue regeneration
- It reduces and even prevents muscle pain
- It increases muscle flexibility
- It breaks the scars and improves their elasticity and adhesion to soft tissues
- It normalizes muscle tension
- It provides access to tissues that are difficult to access for classic stretching
- It prevents injuries [3,4].

When writing about pain relief and improving the condition of the muscle and fascia, the issue of trigger points cannot be ignored. The trigger points are small areas in the form of knots formed on muscle fibers or fascia. It is not difficult to find them during therapy because they are places that are severely sensitive to pain. During oppression it occurs not only in the place of stimulus action, but also radiates or affects to other areas. Most often, trigger points are caused by stress, abnormal posture or abnormal motor patterns, and for athletes as a result of chronic fatigue, training overload or injury. During the SMR, you can relieve such a point from the pain by stopping at place that is sensitive to pain and wait until it "goes away". It is necessary to remember that in this way we do not get rid of muscle tension forever, so SMR should become an important part of the training plan. The combination of two techniques, that is Self Myofascial Release and trigger points autotherapy, gives huge results to the most parts of volleyball players' bodies [5,6,7].

3. Prevention

SMR for both volleyball players and professional athletes is not only an analgesic but also as a prophylaxis. The question that is often asked is: When do you use a roll or ball massage? Is it better before or after training? The answer for that is simple –the best is to do both!! It all depends on the technique, the time, the amount and speed of repetition and the goal we want to achieve. By performing SMR before training, it is best to reach for a foam device with additional spikes that's giving a different stimulation to our muscles, stimulate and warm up them better. It is recommended to perform 5-6 repetitions in a fairly fast but not crazy motion which should provide us with appropriate stretching of the muscles which will result better flexibility of them and increase range of movement in joints. This treatment combined with dynamic stretching should significantly reduce the risk of injury during training [5,8].

On the other hand, the massage after physical activity is best done with a harder and smooth roller, so that the muscles get a little "calm down" after training. In this case free and calm movements are recommended, providing deeper penetration, which will allow for better nourishment of tired, swollen and shortened muscles. The 8-10 repetitions per muscle lot should be performed. In case of a particularly painful place, just hold the pressure for a moment (10 seconds or until the pain goes away) and continue the massage. This post-workout exercise will help to nourish and strengthen the muscle, and in combination with static stretching will make our muscles will be relaxed, elastic and more resistant to injuries [4,7].

4. Regeneration

It is commonly known that massage is a great remedy for tired muscles. All sports clubs who care about the health of their athletes, provide them care of physiotherapist or a massage therapist during the biological regeneration, which is recommended after every match or tournament. Satisfying therapeutic effects can be achieved by using the SMR either after the completion of a training session or a match, but also the day after or whenever we feel that our body needs help to fight against fatigue. Rolling tired muscles just after physical activity will stimulate blood circulation, which will affect into better nutrition, shrink blood vessels to the normal size, transport unnecessary metabolism waste and relax tissues. Thanks to this treatment our body will be less aching or tired and so this will give results as better training readiness the next day. In case when the athlete's body is tired, heavy, swollen and stiff, what happens usually the next day after the workout, it is also a great time for a roller session massage. This will help us to drain the blood from the muscles by getting rid of the feeling of swelling and heaviness and it will gently stretching the muscle fibers helping to reduce the stiffness sense [3,9].

The Polish Plus League Volleyball (Top league in Poland) player plays about 35 games in 8 months. Furthermore, there are countless number of training sessions, which shows that regeneration time is not that much. If a player wants to be in good physical disposition throughout the whole season he must take care of the regeneration of his own body. The regeneration time should be treated not only as a break from physical activity, but as seriously as a training unit. They need to do all what is necessary to be rested and ready for the next workout. When it comes to regeneration in volleyball, the related important issue is the right amount of sleep and diet, and also is worth to remember the aspect of "hygiene of muscles". It is not at all about showering after workout, but about proper exercises such as stretching or massage [7,10].

5. Exercises

The basic theoretical issues needed to start the exercises are already known. Time for practical use of massage instruments. You can roll almost whole body. Important is that, the bones and joints should not be squeezed, and special care should be taken when developing the muscle attachment. Below you will find postures for exercises, remember that this therapy is painful and it is normal, more painful places should be developed with particular accuracy according to the principles discussed in the preceding paragraphs [5,6,7].

Foot (plantar fascia)

Work is between the heel and the toes.

Calf (muscle triceps surae)

Rolling starts above the heel and ends just below the popliteal.

The front part of shin (muscle tibialis anterior)

Rolling starts above the ankle on the left side of the tibia and ends just below the lateral condyle the same bone.

The back part of thigh (muscle biceps femoris)

We start work on the poplite bottom and finish on the ischial tuberosity

The front part of thigh (muscle quadriceps femoris)

The massage starts gently above the top of the patellar, ending just below the anterior superior iliac spine

The lateral part of thigh (iliotibial band)

We start on the lateral surface of the thigh above the knee (the area of the epicondylus lateralis) massage to the area of the anterior superior iliac spine. It is worth focusing more on the muscle tensor fascia lata, because relaxation of this muscle is able to relax the whole band.

The inside part of thigh (the group of adductor muscles)

Movement takes place from the medial epicondylus of the femur and goes towards the pubic bone

Buttocks (the group of gluteus muscles and piriformis muscle)

The massage starts in the area of the greater trochanter femur bone and going up to the upper edge of the hip plate. To work on pear muscle, focus on the area of the greater trochanter femur bone to the outer margin of the sacral bone.

Back (erector spinae muscle)

Movement occurs between the upper part of the sacral bone to the upper vertebrae of the thoracic spine.

Area of shoulder (shoulder muscles)

Rolling around the shoulder area is technically difficult to perform, but volleyball players often have muscle aches, especially those responsible for rotation in the shoulder joint. The best solution to the problem of muscle tension is to treat the trigger points by squeezing the painful point without moving the ball.

Forearm (muscles flexor carpi ulnaris and flexor digitorum longus)

The work takes place between the ulnar styloid process and the medial epicondylus of the humerus.

Neck (rhomboid muscle)

One of the examples used in which the massage device remains in place, and the movement only performs the body. Neck based on roller and head alternates left and right.

6. The choice of SMR equipment

The market is filled with a variety of accessories for analgesic self therapy. From classic balls, through sticks, well-known rollers to less known, but invaluable in action duoballes. It is important to properly select the type, size, shape and hardness of the equipment to the area of the body or individual preferences of each organism such as muscle tone, pain tolerance and muscle mass. During choosing equipment we should consider which one will be most suitable for our problems. The obvious thing is that no one buys all kinds of balls and rolls right away, but chooses one universal accessory. Starting the practice with this type of massage the most proper will be a roller. It is important to remember that equipment with studs are perfect for stimulating the muscles before workout, and against after physical activity the smooth surfaces at equipment combined with slow movements help us to relax our muscles. Balls are used in the development of single more precise structures such as single muscle, for example piriformis muscle, plantar aponeurosis, forearm and shoulder girdle. Perfect for the function of the massage balls are played tennis balls or lacrosse or hard rubber balls for the dog. Rollers are versatile because they allow you to develop any structure. However, as a result of massaging a large area, the penetration is not deep so far for some of the muscle it is not very effective. Rollers are perfect for massaging pelvic limbs, gluteuses or back muscles. Referring to the back, the best solution for working with the erector spine muscles is barely known Duoball. This is a special device that looks like a peanut or a horizontal eight. The shape of this device allows for a deep impact on the tissues near spine without pressure on its bony structure. When

there is no possibility of buying Duoball, but we want to test how this device works, we can glue two tennis balls with a strong adhesive tape and get a prototype of this device. However, the best option is to purchase original equipment, because this is an investment in the health, well-being and results that rewards the cost of massage instruments [5,2,9].

7. Summary

SMR offers significant benefits in return for the time spent working with the body. By doing the exercises in accordance with the rules and recommendations we can easily modify the purpose we want to achieve. This therapy uses similar treatment on the body in different situations to meet the current needs. Another advantage of SMR is the fact that there is no need for specialized equipment - in this case only imagination and creativity could be a constraint. The everyday stuff used in the right way can turn into great massage instruments. All that need to be done to achieve truly satisfying results is just follow some simple and logical rules without complicated assumptions. SMR is a noteworthy solution for everyday sportsman problems [4,10].

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.